

Enhancing Healthcare Data Confidentiality through Decentralized TEE Attestation

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Abstract—The integration of digital technologies like the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) and Electronic Health Records (EHRs) in healthcare has significantly improved patient care. However, this digital transformation brings challenges, particularly regarding the security and privacy of sensitive health information. This paper presents a potential solution to these challenges by combining Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) with a decentralized attestation mechanism. Unlike traditional centralized attestation, the proposed approach leverages blockchain technology to ensure transparency, immutability, and enhanced security. This research outlines the benefits, discusses potential threats to validity, and suggests future work to further secure healthcare data processing, ultimately aiming to create a more robust and resilient system for protecting sensitive patient information.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the healthcare sector has increasingly relied on digital technologies to enhance the quality and efficiency of patient care. This digital transformation involves the use of Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) devices and Electronic Health Records (EHRs) to collect, store, and analyze medical data [1], [2]. According to Grand View Research, the global eHealth market was valued at USD 346.87 billions in 2023, and it is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 18.2% from 2024 to 2030, driven by the need to manage regulatory compliance and rising healthcare costs [3]. While this technological evolution offers significant benefits, such as improved monitoring capabilities and personalized treatment plans [4], [5], it also introduces substantial risks related to the security, privacy, and confidentiality of sensitive health information [6], [7], [8].

Among the others, unauthorized access to healthcare data can have particular severe consequences, compromising patient privacy and potentially endangering their safety. Ensuring the confidentiality of healthcare data is therefore crucial, given its highly personal nature and the potential consequences of exploitation.

Above all, the computation of sensitive health data is particularly challenging and demands rigorous oversight, especially when processed in untrusted environments, which can expose these critical data to significant security vulnerabilities. This

aspect of data handling is of paramount importance as it directly impacts the confidentiality and integrity of health information that is vital for both patient safety and compliance with regulatory standards. [9]. To mitigate these risks, one approach involves using Homomorphic Encryption (HE) [10], which allows computations on encrypted data. This technique allows sensitive information to remain encrypted throughout its processing, thus ensuring that the data's confidentiality is not compromised even in potentially insecure or hostile environments. However, while Homomorphic Encryption offers substantial benefits in securing data operations, it also comes with significant limitations. It is known for its high computational overhead, which can make it impractical for time-sensitive applications. Additionally, the limited range of operations that can be performed on encrypted data poses challenges for its deployment in complex medical data processing tasks that require diverse computational capabilities.

An alternative and more efficient solution is the use of Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) [11], [12], [13]. TEEs provide secure areas within computing hardware where data can be processed and analyzed securely, isolating sensitive operations from the main operating system. This isolation protects against external attacks and software vulnerabilities. The effectiveness of TEEs hinges on the attestation process, which ensures that data processing occurs in a secure and unaltered state by verifying the integrity of the environment. However, current TEE implementations rely on centralized attestation, which can introduce risks such as attestation failures and potential report corruption. These issues are particularly critical in healthcare, where ensuring regulatory compliance and safeguarding patient data are critical.

The main scope of the present research is to raise awareness of such issue, and propose a possible solution to ensure that the attestation process is transparent, immutable, and free from the risks associated with centralization. Our proposed architecture leverages decentralized attestation mechanisms to enhance the security and reliability of healthcare data processing. It integrates IoMT devices for data capture, Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) in the edge layer for secure computations, and blockchain technology for decentralized

verification. Attestation data, including Proofs of Execution (PoEs), is verified by smart contracts and recorded on the blockchain, ensuring an immutable and transparent audit trail. This approach mitigates risks associated with centralized attestation and enhances the confidentiality and integrity of sensitive healthcare data.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II overviews the related work in the field of healthcare data security. Section III provides a detailed explanation of the enabling technologies behind our research. Section IV and V contain the problem statement and use case of interest, respectively. In Section VI, we describe the proposed approach. Section VII discusses its advantages, potential threats to validity, and future work. Finally, Section VIII concludes the paper by summarizing our key findings and contributions.

II. RELATED WORK

Recent advancements in decentralizing TEE attestation have emerged in both industrial applications and academic research. A notable example is AUTOMATA¹, an industrial solution that decentralizes TEE attestation using a blockchain-based protocol, distributing trust across multiple entities to ensure verifiable, immutable processes. It supports Intel SGX to provide a robust root of trust for secure attestations.

In academic research, OPERA [14] by Chen et al. improves Intel's SGX attestation by eliminating the reliance on Intel's centralized service, enabling faster, independent attestations with enhanced privacy. Similarly, JANUS [15] by Zhang et al. decentralizes TEE attestation through blockchain and PUFs, using smart contracts for secure verification and auditing.

In the healthcare field, Wang et al. [16] and Chen et al. [17] utilized SGX for securing IoT environments and remote monitoring services, while Gao et al. [18] combined SGX and blockchain to secure data processing at the edge. Liu et al. [19] proposed a middleware for securely sharing sensor data using differential privacy within a TEE.

Despite these advances, challenges remain in addressing centralized attestation, highlighting the need for further research.

III. ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES

This section provides an overview of the context and key technologies that form the foundation of the proposed approach.

A. Trusted Execution Environment

The adoption of TEEs is increasing in various sectors, including eHealth, to ensure data and code confidentiality and integrity through hardware-based mechanisms. TEEs are secure areas within a processor that create an isolated execution space for sensitive computations, safeguarding against tampering and unauthorized access, even if the main operating system or hypervisor is compromised [20].

Intel's SGX, a prominent TEE technology example, enables the creation of secure enclaves that perform critical

computations. An essential feature of SGX is the enclave attestation mechanism, which includes both local and remote attestation processes integrated into the system's operations. Local attestation occurs within the same system, where part of the application outside the enclave verifies its correct initialization and uncompromised state through a "report." This report includes details like the enclave's identifier and a cryptographic hash of its current state, authenticated by the SGX component in the processor before proceeding with sensitive operations.

Remote attestation extends this verification to external entities, crucial for cloud computing or when engaging third-party services that require high trust. It involves the enclave producing a "quote," similar to the local report but designed for external verification. This quote is sent to a trusted party, typically through Intel's Attestation Service (IAS), which checks the signature, validates the enclave's secure loading on an authentic SGX processor, and confirms the software's integrity. Upon successful verification, the IAS issues an attestation token to affirm the enclave's legitimacy and integrity to external parties.

B. Blockchain Technology

According to the definitions set by ISO/TC 307 [21], a distributed ledger is a register shared across a set of nodes, synchronized through a consensus mechanism. Building upon these definitions, blockchain constitutes a distributed ledger configured into blocks. These blocks are arranged in a sequential, append-only manner cryptographically linked to ensure tamper resistance.

In a blockchain, each block is linked in sequence within a network of participants who do not necessarily need to trust one another. Each block references its predecessor by including its hash, alongside its own data and hash. This structure securely encapsulates the encrypted details of the transactions between parties that led to the data being recorded, aiming to produce a definitive and immutable record.

One of the key features of blockchain technology is the use of "smart contracts", where the terms of the agreement directly written into code. Smart contracts automatically enforce and execute the terms of a contract based on a set of predefined rules minimizing the need for intermediaries and reducing the potential for human error. In healthcare, smart contracts can automate and streamline complex processes, such as the management of consent forms, claims processing, and compliance verification. The transformative application of blockchain in healthcare extends beyond just automation. By enhancing security and integrity for medical data management, blockchain technology ensures the immutability and traceability of medical records, supports the management of consent forms, and tracks prescriptions. Additionally, it secures the medical supply chain by recording data hashes and database indices on the blockchain, thus preserving data integrity and confidentiality. This decentralized approach not only mitigates risks associated with centralized data storage but also streamlines compliance with regulatory standards,

¹<https://www.ata.network/>

offering a robust mechanism for verifying the integrity of health records, ensuring that healthcare systems remain secure, transparent, and efficient.

IV. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Attestation in TEEs is crucial for verifying the integrity and authenticity of applications running within them. However, current TEE RA designs have significant limitations due to their reliance on a centralized trust model. This model depends on a single provisioned secret key and a centralized verifier to establish trust with remote parties. Specifically, Intel's SGX utilizes a centralized attestation mechanism through the IAS. This centralized approach presents significant concerns, especially when applied to sectors dealing with highly sensitive data, such as healthcare. Dependence on a single authority introduces a single point of failure and raises questions about the attestation provider's trustworthiness and impartiality.

The primary issues with current TEE RA schemes include [15]:

- 1) Over-Centralization:
 - **Single Root of Trust (RoT):** Reliance on a single provisioned hardware key makes the system vulnerable to advanced attacks. Once this key is compromised, the integrity of the entire attestation process is at risk.
 - **Single Verifier Dependency:** The verification process is centralized, meaning a compromised verifier can falsely attest compromised applications as trustworthy or vice versa, without allowing relying parties to independently re-verify the results.
- 2) Lack of Flexibility and Resilience:
 - **Fixed Procedures:** Current schemes lack the flexibility to adapt to different needs for availability and Quality of Service (QoS). They are vulnerable to network outages, device malfunctions, and computing exhaustion, leading to failures in cloud infrastructures.

While decentralized attestation for TEEs such as Intel's SGX has been implemented in various sectors, to the best of our knowledge, its application within healthcare remains unexplored. The existing literature and practices have not yet extended decentralized attestation mechanisms to the healthcare domain, where they could mitigate these risks by reducing dependency on any single authority. This oversight represents a gap in ensuring the integrity and security of sensitive health data, with potentially severe implications for patient confidentiality and trust in health systems. This paper introduces a preliminary architectural schema aimed at adapting decentralized attestation to healthcare. The goal is to outline the potential benefits and framework of applying decentralized attestation specifically to healthcare applications, setting the stage for future research and development.

V. THE HEALTHCARE USE CASE

Management of patients with health problems implies the involvement of several professional figures, considering that

multiple information need to be collected for the same patient, both during diagnostic and follow-up phases. Clinicians from various specialties, surgeons, biologists, technicians and administrative support figures are involved in the process. In this scenario, a database is set up for patients with thyroid cancer and it is finally managed by the Oncology department responsible for the patient's follow-up. The database contains both demographic data and empty columns which correspond to biochemical data, possible surgery procedure information and imaging methods. Once thyroid cancer diagnosis is confirmed, for each patient, histological sub-type, genetic mutations, staging, possible radiometabolic therapy, follow-up images and tumor markers are collected at different time-points and included in the database by the healthcare professionals listed above. In each column, every patient will have a certain categorical or continue value, describing any single clinical characteristic. The combination of the different values in the cells of the database determines the risk stratification of each patient. When some of the columns show specific values (i.e. indicating the presence of a certain gene mutation or metastatic disease), then the patient ID must be reported and highlighted to the Oncologist who will decide whether the patient needs a more tighten follow-up.

A significant security issue arises if these sensitive health data or the computations performed on them are exposed or intercepted by unauthorized entities. For example, if the data or computation results were to be captured by a health insurance agency, they could potentially misuse this sensitive information. The agency could make decisions on providing or denying insurance coverage based on the patient's medical conditions, such as specific genetic mutations or the presence of metastatic disease. This misuse of confidential health data would not only violate patient privacy but also lead to unfair and discriminatory practices, ultimately harming the patients.

Given the gravity of these potential security breaches, it is crucial to ensure that all computations involving sensitive health data are performed in secure environments. This need for secure computation is essential to protect patient privacy and prevent the exploitation of health data for unethical purposes.

VI. PROPOSED APPROACH

This section elaborates on the proposed approach, which is based on decentralized TEE attestation to enhance the confidentiality of healthcare data management. As shown in Figure 1, the proposed solution integrates a multi-layered architecture involving IoMT devices, TEEs, blockchain technology and a cloud layer.

A. System Components and Workflow

The proposed architecture is composed of the following key components:

- **IoMT Devices and Infrastructures:** These include sensors and infrastructures operating within the healthcare sector that are responsible for generating and handling data.

Fig. 1. The architecture depicts a secure healthcare data system. IoMT devices capture data, which is processed by TEEs in the Edge Layer. Provers generate Proofs of Execution, verified by the On-Chain Attestation layer using smart contracts. Verified attestation data is recorded on the blockchain, while the Cloud Layer provides additional resources.

- **Edge Layer TEE:** Each device at the edge layer contains a TEE where sensitive computations are performed. Before any computation, the TEE must be registered to a network with other TEEs. This registration is essential for accessing the network and ensuring that the device can participate in decentralized computations and attestation processes.
- **Provers** Within each TEE, a 'Prover' functions as a specialized entity responsible for generating a Proof of Execution (PoE) and attestation reports. These reports are crucial for verifying that the computations within the TEE are executed securely and without any alterations. After registration, the TEE performs the required computation. Upon completing the computation, the TEE generates a PoE. Simultaneously, other TEEs (provers) perform the same computation and generate their own PoEs. These PoEs serve as cryptographic proofs that the computation was executed correctly and securely.

- **On-Chain Attestation and Verifier Contract:** After the attestation reports are generated, they are sent to the blockchain network for verification. The Verifier performs several critical checks. It ensures the validity and consistency of all PoEs related to the same computation by cross-verifying them across different TEEs. The Verifier also checks the public key of each TEE to confirm it is registered within the network and conducts a security attestation to ensure the TEE is operating securely within expected parameters. The on-chain attestation mechanism uses smart contracts (Verifier Contract) to verify the integrity and authenticity of the attestation reports automatically. This decentralized verification process ensures that the attestation is transparent, immutable, and free from centralization risks. Once these checks are complete, the attestation data (including PoEs and verification status) is recorded on the blockchain, providing an immutable and transparent audit trail.
- **Cloud Layer:** This layer serves as a supportive infrastructure for additional computational resources and storage, interacting with the edge layer to manage data overflow or intensive computational tasks that cannot be handled at the edge.

B. Data Flow and Security

The data flow of the proposed architecture starts at the IoMT devices, where initial data capture and preliminary processing occur. From there, data is securely transmitted to the TEEs in the edge layer for further processing. Each TEE generates an attestation report, which is then verified through the on-chain attestation process managed by smart contracts. This ensures that every computational step and data transaction is recorded and verified on the blockchain, providing a transparent and secure mechanism for managing healthcare data.

This architecture effectively addresses the challenges of centralized attestation models by distributing trust across multiple nodes in the blockchain, enhancing the resilience and reliability of the data verification process. The separation of computation and verification roles also aids in maintaining the system's integrity and independence, ensuring that healthcare data management is both secure and efficient.

Specifically, the workflow follows four different steps: secure computation, generation of attestation reports, decentralized attestation process, and computation independence.

1) *Secure Computation:* Secure computation ensures that sensitive health data is processed within a trusted and protected environment. All computational operations involving sensitive health data are executed within Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) located in the edge layer, such as on edge nodes or edge servers. This arrangement ensures that data remains protected against unauthorized access or tampering during processing. By utilizing TEEs in the edge layer, we minimize the exposure of sensitive data to external threats and reduce the reliance on centralized computational resources, thereby enhancing data security and privacy.

2) *Generation of Attestation Reports*: To verify the integrity of the computations performed within the TEEs, our approach involves the generation of detailed attestation reports. These reports serve as proof that the data processing has occurred in a secure manner. Each TEE generates an attestation report that includes cryptographic proofs of the secure environment, details of the computations performed, and the integrity of the data involved. These reports provide assurance that the data has been processed within a secure and tamper-proof environment, maintaining the confidentiality and integrity of sensitive health information.

3) *Decentralized Attestation Process*: The primary innovation of the proposed solution lies in decentralizing the attestation process, eliminating the risks associated with a centralized attestation authority.

The attestation reports generated by the TEEs are transmitted to the blockchain for verification. The framework utilizes a decentralized network of nodes and smart contracts on a blockchain to verify the integrity and authenticity of the attestation reports. This process ensures that the verification is transparent, immutable, and free from centralization risks. Multiple independent nodes participate in the verification process, distributing the trust and eliminating single points of failure. Smart contracts on the blockchain automate the verification process, ensuring that the attestation reports are validated according to predefined rules and criteria.

4) *Computation Independence*: In this approach, all computational tasks and their verification are decoupled, promoting local control and decentralization. The computation of healthcare data is performed within TEEs in the edge layer, ensuring that sensitive data remains within a secure environment. The On-Chain Attestation layer is solely responsible for the verification and recording of the attestation reports, not for performing the computations themselves. This separation ensures that the computational tasks are securely handled within the TEEs, while the verification benefits from a decentralized mechanism.

For practical implementation, we have considered using the Automata framework, which offers decentralized network management, blockchain integration, and scalability. This framework supports the requirements of our proposed decentralized attestation system in healthcare.

VII. DISCUSSION

This section discusses the advantages of the proposed solution, addresses potential threats to its validity, and outlines future work to enhance and expand the framework.

A. Advantages

Among the others, the proposed solution offers enhanced security in various aspects. To begin with, by decentralizing the attestation process, the reliance on a single authority (e.g., Intel) for TEE attestation is eliminated. This reduces the risk of single points of failure and potential corruption by a centralized entity. Additionally, Blockchain technology ensures that attestation reports are immutable and transparent.

Once recorded on the blockchain, these reports cannot be altered, providing a reliable and tamper-proof audit trail. Also, all computational tasks involving sensitive health data are performed locally within TEEs on the user's devices. This minimizes the exposure of sensitive data to external threats and ensures that data processing remains under the user's control. Transparency and trust are further advantages provided. The use of a decentralized network of nodes and smart contracts for verification ensures that the attestation process is transparent. Each step of the verification process is recorded on the blockchain, making it auditable and increasing trust in the system. Then, since the verification process is distributed across multiple independent nodes, the system's resilience and trustworthiness are improved. This distribution reduces the risk of collusion or corruption by any single entity.

Our framework is also highly scalable. The proposed decentralized network can scale with the number of nodes, improving the efficiency and speed of the attestation verification process. This scalability is crucial for handling the increasing volume of health data generated by IoT devices.

B. Threats to Validity

Despite the numerous advantages, there are potential threats to the validity of our proposed solution that must be considered. First, the reliability of the decentralized verification process depends on the availability and performance of the nodes in the network. Ensuring a sufficient number of active and honest nodes is critical to maintaining the integrity of the verification process. The decentralized nature of the network may also introduce latency in the verification process. This could impact the timeliness of attestation, especially in scenarios requiring real-time verification. Among security challenge, it is important to take into consideration that smart contracts, while secure, are not immune to vulnerabilities. Bugs or exploits in the smart contracts used for attestation verification could compromise the integrity of the verification process. Lastly, the decentralized network may be vulnerable to Sybil attacks, where a single entity controls multiple nodes to gain undue influence over the verification process. Implementing robust mechanisms to detect and mitigate such attacks is essential.

C. Future Work

The present research provides the starting point for further experimentation. Possible improvements include the development of mechanisms for dynamic management of nodes, which can help maintain a sufficient number of active and honest nodes. This includes incentivizing node participation and implementing strategies to handle node failures. Exploring methods to optimize the latency of the decentralized verification process is a crucial aspect as well. This may involve enhancing the efficiency of smart contract execution and optimizing network communication protocols. Regularly auditing the smart contracts used in the verification process can help identify and mitigate potential vulnerabilities. Implementing automated tools for smart contract verification can

enhance the security of the system. Then, implementing robust mechanisms to detect and prevent Sybil attacks is essential. This may include identity verification of nodes, reputation-based systems, and stake-based mechanisms to ensure that nodes act honestly.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The paper highlights the critical importance of securing healthcare data in the digital age, focusing on the issues introduced by centralized attestation mechanisms in TEEs. We proposed a novel approach using decentralized attestation with blockchain technology, ensuring transparency, immutability, and enhanced security of the attestation process. Our solution distributes trust across multiple entities, reducing risks associated with single points of failure and potential corruption. By processing sensitive health data locally within TEEs and employing a decentralized verification process, the proposed framework enhances security and user control over data.

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